

Artificial Intelligence – The New Face of Human Resource Recruitment

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In Calcalist, it was published that in a survey conducted among organizations, it was found that at least 92% of recruitment managers responded that they had used artificial intelligence for employee recruitment, 7% of respondents said they intend to start using artificial intelligence in the recruitment process soon, and only one percent had neither used nor intended to use artificial intelligence for recruitment. Fortune magazine reported that at least 492 out of 500 companies on the Fortune list use artificial intelligence for employee recruitment. At first glance, it seems that artificial intelligence can help human resource recruiters sift through dozens, sometimes hundreds or even thousands of resumes, but what dangers arise from excessive and irresponsible use of artificial intelligence alone in recruitment?

Biases: In a U.S. court, it was found that artificial intelligence favored people with white skin color as suitable for the position. Amazon used artificial intelligence for a short period that favored men over women in hiring for engineering positions. It was found that artificial intelligence sometimes suffers from bias, which causes it to prefer certain criteria without real justification. Researchers claim that these biases stem from the data fed into artificial intelligence and from the training of the artificial intelligence, such that if the AI trainers had biases, they transferred them to the artificial intelligence during the training.

Recruitment in a nutshell: As is known, recruitment and staffing in human resources consists of four main staffing tools: biographical data, letters of recommendation, interview, and test. Biographical data are the "dry" details of the candidate, such as personal details, education, work experience, hobbies, etc., usually appearing in the

resume. This data serves the organization according to the approach that past behavior predicts future behavior.

Predictors and indicators: In the first two stages of recruitment, human resource recruiters place before them a list of predictors, which indicate the employees with the best chances to fulfill their role, integrate, and adapt to their work. For example, in an organization seeking long-term employees, they may not necessarily want a worker who has not stayed long in jobs; therefore, one predictor is the length of time the candidate stayed in their previous jobs. In an office with strict dress and arrival rules, one predictor will be the candidate's arrival on time and in appropriate dress. For a role requiring open-mindedness and diversity, predictors will include broad education and varied interests. For a role requiring work with the public, the predictor will be interpersonal skills evident from a personal interview. These predictors help organizations make informed decisions about the candidate's ability to integrate into the organization and adapt to their work. Conversely, predictors are not 100% accurate, and one cannot always rely on a single predictor to conclude the candidate's chances of adapting to their job.

Equal Employment Opportunities Law: Section 2(a) of the law prohibits discriminating against a job seeker in hiring due to "their gender, sexual orientation, personal status, pregnancy, fertility treatments, in-vitro fertilization treatments, being a parent, Age, Race, Religious belief, nationality, country of origin, place of residence, views, political party, or military reserve service." The law derives from the Basic Law: Human Dignity and Liberty, and from the values of equality it protects. It is intended to prevent biases in hiring based on criteria, or predictors, that are not legally valid for consideration. The U.S. Equal Employment Opportunity Commission (EEOC) declared that artificial intelligence causes repeated and persistent discrimination, and although technologies develop rapidly, workplaces must remember that there are still laws to prevent such discrimination. Therefore, several regulations were proposed for supervision and intervention in the algorithms of artificial intelligences involved in human resource recruitment. In the

European Union's Artificial Intelligence Act (EU AI Act), they also addressed the dangers arising from irresponsible use of artificial intelligence in hiring and noted that most AI biases were rooted in the legal prohibitions on discrimination in hiring, biases based on race, gender, age, and ethnic origin.

Regulation: To enable companies to continue using artificial intelligence, it is necessary to adapt them to the laws and regulations underlying the Equal Rights in Employment Law, so that artificial intelligence complies with the law, both at the algorithm level and the training level. In addition, attention must be paid to individual rights and privacy protection when collecting and processing a person's private information; generally, consent is required. The Privacy Protection Law states in Section 1 that one shall not infringe upon another's privacy without their consent. An infringement of privacy is listed in Section 2 and in sub-sections (7), (8), and (9), which refer to violating the duty of confidentiality and disclosing information about a person's private affairs. Provisions regarding a "database," a collection of data held for computerized processing, are also listed in the law and case law. The GDPR, the European privacy protection regulations, lists dozens of strict laws intended to prevent violations in storing and processing databases and personal information, including the "right to be forgotten": the right to delete personal information from any database. Maintaining data security, numerous prohibitions on transferring databases and personal information insecurely, and numerous prohibitions on exporting the personal information of European residents protected under the AI Act outside Europe.

In conclusion, to begin moving toward regulation in the use of artificial intelligence in human resource recruitment, there is a need for supervision and intervention, at the programming and training levels, so that the artificial intelligence collecting and processing information from candidates: 1. Holds consent from the candidate; 2. Is free from biases contrary to the law, case law, and human logic; 3. Ensures that the processed and unprocessed information is stored securely and can be deleted at the candidate's request.